

“COMPANION PROTECTION” PROJECT FOR WOMEN

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Abstract. Today, there are many reforms for women in Uzbekistan. In this regard, we want to offer the most modern and effective project for women. Before talking about our application, I wanted to give a little information about psychotherapy. What is psychotherapy? When is it used? Who uses it? Why do we need him? We answer such questions. What is psychotherapy?

Keywords: depression, mobile application, psychological, psychotherapist.

Psychotherapy is about changing the thoughts, beliefs, feelings, and behaviors that may be causing discomfort and mental health problems in the patient being treated. The psychologist listens to the sufferings, difficulties, problems and doubts of the patient, confirming the expression of what he really experienced. In addition, with the work of the psychologist, the patient puts at his disposal various methods, for example, problem processing, open questions, self-situational exercises, verbalization of words. All these methods can change depending on the flow of the psychologist, they are cognitive-behavioral, psychoanalytic, humanistic... The main goal of using these methods is to achieve changes in the patient, to develop new, healthy and effective habits. Allows to increase their well-being. To create. This is achieved by confronting the patient himself, his problems, qualities and shortcomings in a psychotherapeutic context, as well as by using methods learned through counseling. The main goal of the procedure is to ensure that the patient lives a happy, healthy and productive life.

When is it necessary?

There are still many myths surrounding psychotherapy in popular culture, one of which is that "seeing a psychologist is for crazy people." Also, it is a plus to consult a psychologist for problems that can be solved at home or in the circle of acquaintances. Others may think they are fine and do not need the help of a mental health professional. However, whether you are dealing with serious psychological problems or want to gain more control over your life, going to psychotherapy is always a good choice. It is necessary to overcome the fear of consulting a psychologist, especially if someone considers that, sometimes, something that has a relatively easy solution in the hands of a professional, for example, due to momentary episodes of depression, anxiety or anger attacks. Psychotherapy is also recommended for those suffering from serious illnesses. Referral to a psychotherapist is recommended for conditions such as cancer, HIV/AIDS, morbid obesity, terminal illness, limb loss, amyotrophic lateral atrophy (ALS), hearing and/or vision impairment.. Although consultation with a psychologist is not a cure for the disease, it helps a person to accept the process, to look at life optimistically and constructively, or to learn strategies for coping with a chronic illness. Another reason why you should go to psychotherapy is that it has nothing to do with psychopathology or medical conditions, but if you do not get the right help, it can harm the health of the participants, such as divorce, children leaving, , not feeling fulfilled in studies or work, or losing a loved one.

The most important features of psychotherapy are the establishment of a strong therapeutic alliance between the patient and the therapist. It is in this way that the patient contributes to the creation of a warm atmosphere in which he is sincere and, in addition to releasing his irrational beliefs, explains everything that happened to him. With this, the psychologist tries to develop a strategy for changing inappropriate behavior patterns, irrational fears, dysphoric feelings, and disturbed ways of communicating with others.

Development of treatment

Clinical psychologists are trained to administer and interpret various types of tests, such as personality and intelligence tests, as well as questionnaires to diagnose general disorder, depression, anxiety, and other psychological problems. After the patient answers the tests, no

matter what, the psychologist has objective information about him. According to the results of these tests, it is possible to diagnose exactly what the patient's problem is, as well as to know the personality characteristics of the patient, if they have high talent or, on the contrary, suffer from a personality disorder or intellectual disease. disability. based on all the received information, the psychologist can create a script on how the treatment process will continue. At the first stage of the process, the psychologist helps the patient to determine the state of his problem. In addition, he will explain to you how the therapy will proceed and how many times a week you should visit. This part of the process usually takes place during the first sessions, which can last from one to three or four sessions, depending on the tests performed and the complexity of the patient's problem.

After overcoming this stage, a measure is taken which is a solution to the problems. For this, both the patient and the therapist work together, although in an asymmetric and professional relationship, because the psychologist has expert knowledge and knows what strategies to use. This phase of therapy involves finding effective ways for the patient to think, behave, and feel in order to cope with life's challenges. During the sessions, the psychologist may ask the patient to perform exercises to dramatize the newly learned behavior. It also asks you to repeat them at home or in a problematic situation. As the treatment continues, the psychologist and the patient observe whether there is a real process or whether there is a need to reconstruct the initial goals.

Confidentiality

Confidentiality and respect for the privacy of the patient are the basis for the psychologist's professional activity and are part of the deontological code of the profession. Indeed, a clinical psychologist who violates patient confidentiality may be disqualified. With this in mind, patients should not worry about what they might say in a psychotherapeutic context, they should be completely open about their most intimate thoughts and behaviors. and can speak honestly.

Effectiveness of psychotherapy

About 75 percent of people who receive psychotherapy experience some benefit, usually between 6 and 12 years. Also, a comparison was made between 80% of people who go to a psychologist and those who do not. those who participated in psychotherapy felt significantly better at the end of treatment.

End of process

Individuals with severe and chronic mental illness may require indefinite psychotherapy along with pharmacology and visits to a psychiatrist. assess whether they are suffering from adverse drug reactions. Regular psychotherapy sessions can provide the support needed to maintain daily functioning despite an unfortunately chronic condition.

Other people may turn to psychotherapy despite their problems being resolved. This is because they gain a better understanding of life, well-being, and continue to feel better by following a psychotherapist. Going to the psychologist, if he is fine, not to look for problems that we don't have, but as a way to make sure that he is fine, like who goes to the doctor for a checkup or who? he goes to the dentist to have his teeth cleaned.

Psychotherapy consists in finding correct and objective solutions to human problems. The program we are preparing will provide great practical help in this direction. This app is being created to provide diagnosis, counseling and necessary treatment support to women who are experiencing difficult life situations. Our application process is completed in 4 stages. First, the user installs the application on his mobile phone. Then he will register in the application, that is, after entering the region, city, age, gender, name, the application will complete its work.

Our user chooses one of the main reasons. This shows what is the main cause of the problems in it. To show the reasons for this, it is permissible to focus on statistical data. For example, divorces, HIV AIDS, abortion, addiction, mental recovery, loss of loved ones (husband, children), various family problems, disagreements, oncology, etc. From the section, the user selects the necessary category of the problem that applies to him and goes to the key stage of the application. Statistical information about problems in the categories will also be provided in our application. Cause The user should have the necessary information about the cause of the problem. Then our result will

be to find a solution to the problem. In this, the most qualified psychotherapists use treatment procedures. For complete information on the treatment process, please refer to Treatment Needed. There will be complete information about how long the processing will take, how to do it, what to pay attention to during the treatment. For this, not only a few psychotherapists, but many psychotherapists' treatment courses will be qualified psychologists' accompanying courses. In addition, we can say that if the user wants, it will be possible to contact our psychotherapists and psychologists. Communication with our experts is all done anonymously. the benefit will be a secret for the private expert. It will only be disclosed to our personal psychotherapists if the user chooses to contact our experts. If the user is unable to meet with our security expert, the user can be connected to the best support expert.

Application Features

User profile:

- A personal account in which, after passing a couple of tests, a psychological portrait of the user is formed (it helps to choose the right psychologist / psychotherapist)
- Selection of a psychologist / psychotherapist
- Anonymous chat with a psychotherapist
- Individual recommendations
- ...

Recommendations:

7. Stress Relief Tips
8. Proper nutrition
9. Meditation Lessons
10. Proper breathing
11. ...

The result of using the application will be:

- reduction of social tension in society and, as a result, a decrease in divorce proceedings;
- correct assessment of the place of women in society;
- increasing the role of psychotherapists in the normalization of interpersonal and family relationships;
- reducing the level of distrust of the population in the medical services provided.

Features and functions of the mobile application, development environment, target audience .

In our last step, our user can read the answers to the most frequently asked questions and therefore get answers by sending the questions that interest him to the experts. The best part of our application is the anonymous application of the user, on the other hand, our application is to help people who need psychotherapists living in places where the internet network is not yet fully reached. as well as further development of literacy in people. There are still thoughts in people's minds that only mentally ill people turn to psychotherapists and psychologists. to remove such attitudes and to change the attitudes towards psychotherapists and strengthen their confidence in them.

Sources used:

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